

INDIAN BANKING SECTOR – RECENT CHANGES AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract:

The Indian economy's liberalisation in the early 1990-91 has resulted in the conception of various private sector banks. This has sparked as boom in the country's banking sector in the past two decades (2010-2020). The growth of Indian banking system consist of 12 public sector banks, 22 private sector banks, 46 foreign banks, 56 regional rural banks, 1,485 urban cooperative banks and 96,000 rural cooperative banks in addition to cooperative credit institutions in 2020. The total number of ATM's in India increased to 2,09,282. The growth was driven primarily by two factors, first is the influx of Foreign Direct Investment and seconds the conservative policies of the Reserve Bank of India, which have shielded Indian banks from recession and global economic changes.

Key word: Indian Banking Sector, Indian Economy, Recent Changes in Banking Sector.

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Introduction: The banking sector plays a very important role in the development of nation's economy. The growth of banking sector depends upon the rules and regulations of Reserve Bank of India as well as government policies and the customer services given by them in various aspects. As per the Reserve Bank India guidance, India's banking sector is sufficiently capitalized and well regulated. The economic and financial conditions in the nations are far superior to compare any other nations in the world. Liquidity risk, Market and Credit studies the Indian banks are generally resilient and have withstood the globally well. Now days banking sector acts as a backbone of Indian economy which reflects as a supporters during the period of boom and recession. India is

being fundamentally strong supported by concrete decisions, economic policies and implementation by the Indian Government. To develop and improve of the banking sector, Indian government, Reserve Bank of India and ministry of finance have made several notable efforts. The growing trend in banking sector is found noteworthy after the recent economic reforms in India.

Objectives:

1. To understand the Indian banking sector and its components.
2. To know about the various changes in banking sector.
3. To study the impact to be created by changes in banking sector on Indian economy.

Limitations:

Due to certain limitations the topic is expressed is shorten and couldn't explain in depth. The recent changes are considered for the particular paper. The Banking Sector is very wide subject with its depth and breadth all over the world. Therefore, in the present research study, only the effects of the banking sector on the Indian economy have been considered.

Research Methodology:

The research is based on the secondary data which is collected from the various journals, Newspaper, Report of research agencies, related web link, and research reports of the world banks and books. The analytical and statistical research method both are used for the data collection and analysis. The main focus of the study is on recent status and emerges in banking sector and Indian economy.

Recent Changes in Banking Sector:

Indian Banking sector has recently roll out of newly and innovative banking systems like small finance, online payments and online transactions. Reserve bank of India's new guidelines and measures about changes may go a long way in helping the restructuring of the domestic banking industry.

1. **Public sector Asset 2020-21** – The asset of public sector banks stood at Rs. 107. 83 lakh Crore (1.52 Trillion US\$) in financial year 2020. During Financial Year 2016 to Financial Year 2020, bank credit grew at a CAGR of 3.57%. As of Financial Year 2020, total credit extended surged to US\$ 1,698.97 billion. During Financial Year 2016-2020, deposits grew at a CAGR of 13.93% and reached US\$ 1.93 trillion by FY20. According to the RBI, bank credit and bank deposits stood respectively at 108.79 trillion and Rs. 155.14 trillion, as of July 16, 2021. Credit to non-food company

or industries stood at Rs. 107.93 trillion in the month of July 2021.

- 2. Digital Payments system:** The digital revolution has played an important role in shaping the growth of the banking sector in India, from promising customer experience to ensuring extraordinary gains in productivity. The digital payments methods or systems in India has evolved the most among 25 countries with India's Immediate Payment Service being the only system at five in the Faster Payments Innovation Index. The India's real time money transfer (IMPS) platform was facilitated with being the best innovation globally by a United States based research firm Fidelity National Information Services. India's IMPS was rated highest in FIS, FPII hence, claiming the crown of being the best digital innovation worldwide. The FIS announce a FPII annually, based on a scale of 5 to 1 rating scales having 5 is being the highest scale. The measuring on a scale of 5 to 1, the metrics signify the follows.
 1. 5-Level: Indicates additional features employed to maximize customer value.
 2. Level: Indicates highly desirable features aiming at enhanced customer value.
 3. Level: Indicates Fast payments.
- 3. P M Jan Dhan Yojana:** The Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana was a tremendous decision taken by any government so far in India. Banks accounts opened under the governments flagship financial inclusion drive PMJDY reached 40.55 crore and deposits in Jan Dhan Bank accounts stood at more than Rs. 1.30 lakh crore (18.44 billionUS\$). PMJDY is National Mission for financial inclusion to ensure access to financial services namely, Saving deposit Accounts or Banking accounts, Credit, Remittance, Pensions and Insurance in affordable manner.
- 4. Demonetisation:** On 08 November 2016 the government of India announced the demonetization of all 1000 and 500 bank notes of the Mahatma Gandhi series. The proposal by the government involves the elimination of these existing notes from circulation and a gradual replacement with a new set of notes. In the short term it is intended that the cash in circulation would be substantially squeezed since there are limits placed on the amount that individuals can withdraw. The reasons offered for demonetization are two-fold, to control forged notes that could be contributing to terrorism, national security concern and determine or eliminate the black economy.
- 5. MUDRA Bank:** The Micro Units Development and Refinance Agency Ltd. was launched by prime minister on 008 April, 2015 with a corpus of 20,000 crore and a credit guarantee of Rs. 3,000 crore. MUDRA loans are given by commercial Banks,

Small finance banks or institutions, RRB and MFIs. The borrower can approach any of the lending institutions mentioned above or can apply online through portal, under the aegis of MUDRA, PMMY has creates the three segments, The **Shishu** segments-covers loans upto Rs.50,000/-, **Kishor** segments - covers loans above Rs. 50,000/- and upto Rs.5 lakh and **Tarun** segments - covers loan above Rs. 5 lakh and upto Rs. 10 lakh, has create a signify growth and fulfill the needs of the beneficiary and entrepreneurs.

Impact of Changes on Indian Economy:

The rate of economic and development growth of India has started after the economic reforms of 1991 when Indian government adopted policy of LPG. The availability of the new technology and funds are grownup, here drastically change in overall economy but it has not fully success in the rural economy of the country. The above changes helping our financial sector in maintaining stability while helping real economic sector attained inclusive growth.

1. Digital Payments are taking useful steps to make the Indian economy financially viable.

It will enable citizens who have so far only transacted in cash to go for formal banking. Traditional banks have not been able to reach both urban and rural areas but digital banking has made it easier to reach the end customers. All banking transactions have been made possible with the help of a single mobile phone or network. It can be said that the positive impact of the Indian banking changes on the Indian economy. Some of the current digitally enabled government banking or approved banking platforms are given as below:

1. Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM)
2. Unified Payment Interface (UPI)
3. National Unified USSD Platform
4. Aadhar Enabled Payment System

2. Financial inclusion refers to the equality and availability of opportunities to access financial transactions or services. Financial Inclusion act as a key driver in the economic development and growth of country. The government of India is actively propagating financial inclusion through various following schemes.

- Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY)
- Atal Pension Yojana (PMJDY)
- Pradhan Mantri Vaya Vandana Yojana (PMVVY)

- Stand Up India Scheme
 - Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY)
 - Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana (PMSBY)
 - Sukanya Samridhi Yojana
 - Jeevan Suraksha Bandhan Yojana
3. Demonetization impacted positive as well as negative angle on the society and people. For the purpose of exchange old notes many people were forcefully open accounts in banks. Demonetization change created adverse short term policy impact, the real impact must be assessed in the medium or long term impact and it is reduce illegal activities such as generation of black money and corruption from getting chance back into economy. The online shopping leading enterprises have open more saving options on digital payments. Some payments companies also growing their business adoption of online payment facilities.
 4. The Mudra scheme provides and extended finance and credit support to microfinance institutions through regulation and inclusive participation. It has also registered all microfinance institutions and introduced a system of performance rating and accreditations. It has provided structured guidelines for the borrowers to follow to avoid failure of institutions and business, Mudra helps to last borrowers of finance to evaluate and the meet their requirement best.
 5. Durin 2019-2020 scheduled commercial banks registered a robust performance by improved asset quality, return profitability and stronger capital provision. The insolvency and bankruptcy code remained the dominant mode of recovery, reconstruction of financial assets and enforcement of securities interest act channel also improved.
 6. The adoption of core banking solutions for the incorporation of sophisticated technological solutions was an important step towards using technology to enhance the Indian banking sector. It is also facilitated the calculation of maturity, penalties and interest systems. Use of technological integration has been raised a notch higher to enable unprecedented customer experience.
 7. Government Initiatives:
In August 2021, Prime Minister launched e-RUPI, someone and purpose-specific digital payment answer.

- As per Union Budget 2021-22, the govt. can disinvest IDBI Bank and denationalize two public sector banks.
- As per Union Budget 2019-20, the govt. projected absolutely machine-driven GST refund module associated an electronic invoice system that may eliminate the requirement for a separate e-way bill.
- Government swimmingly administrated consolidation, reducing the amount of Public Sector Banks by eight.
- As in month of September 2018, the government of India created PM Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) theme associate open-ended theme and else additional incentives.

Conclusion:

To conclude the changes in banking sector has made a tremendous impact on the Indian economy. Changes made in the Indian banking sector by the government will have a long term impact on the Indian economy in recent years. The digital revolution has played a crucial role in shaping the growth and development of banking sector. The post demonetization phase the finance industry has significantly shifted towards digitization. The Indian banking sector is changed is constantly day by day and these changes have been beneficial for the Indian economy. The competitive environment in India has been strengthened; the overall effect of the proposed changes in the 2012-13 Union budget is becoming positive. These changes are taking place mainly in rural areas and are diving inclusion and credit growth. The efficiency and productivity of public sector banks is increasing and government policies need to be implemented in a sustainable manner. Also, Indian banks need to re-evaluate existing business policies, which could greatly strengthen the Indian banking sector.

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